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**Interdisciplinary solutions for
sustainable buildings**

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Bioinspired living coating system for wood protection: Exploring fungal species on biofinish coated wood surfaces

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The service life of timber products exposed to natural weathering limits the broad use of wood as an external building element. Biofinish is a novel surface finishing solution based on the bioinspired concept designed for effective wood protection. This innovative surface finishing approach enhances the wood's hydrophobicity through oil treatment, resulting in improved dimensional stability. Living cells of *Aureobasidium pullulans* effectively shield wood from deterioration caused by infestation of other competitive fungi. The melanin pigment produced by the fungus provides an appealing dark surface and protects against UV radiation. Another noteworthy advantage of using living cells of *A. pullulans* as a coating system is its remarkable self-healing ability. This property does not exist in any traditional wood protection systems, which distinguishes Biofinish from conventional wood protection methods (Sailer et al., 2010). This study aimed to identify fungal species on the surfaces of in-service wood coated with Biofinish. Additionally, it evaluated Biofinish's protective properties against wood-infesting fungi and assessed the survival and adaptation of *A. pullulans* within the coating during its in-service period. The study was performed on the façade of the InnoRenew CoE building in Izola, Slovenia, following a 9-month exposure period. The façade is comprised of European Larch wood (*Larix decidua*) treated with linseed oil and coated with Biofinish. Swab samples were collected from wood surfaces at 0.5 and 4 meters in all four cardinal directions of the building and cultured on nutrient media. Morphological characteristics and sequencing of PCR-amplified DNA from the ITS regions of rRNA gene clusters were used for fungal identification. The majority of species detected belonged to the Ascomycetes genera *Aureobasidium* and *Cladosporium*. The results indicated the survival of *A. pullulans* within the Biofinish coating after nine months of service.

Keywords: wood treatment, building material, fungal colonisation, self-repairing

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